

microspores excised from male sterile and male fertile panicles at the anther plating stage (i.e., the mid-uninucleate stage).

The callus-forming ability of the anthers of the male sterile lines appears to be related to the stage of pollen abortion (see table). When late abortion occurs (BT cytoplasm), the anther culturability of the male sterile lines is either slightly decreased or not significantly different from control. When male sterility is due to early microspore degeneration (WA cytoplasm), a dramatic decrease in callus production occurs, because the microspore population that undergoes the androgenesis pathway is consistently reduced.

Induction ability of male sterile rice lines and their male fertile homologue lines. Goias, Brazil.

Genotype	Cytoplasm	Callus-forming anthers/anther inoculated ^a	Pollen sterility just before anthesis ^b	Spikelet sterility ^c
		(%)	(%I)	(%)
IRAT313	Normal	5 a	7	21
CNA-IRAT1A	WA	0 b	98	100
IRAT103	Normal	25 a	3	12
CNA-IRAT6A	WA	8b	37	100
CNA-IRAT4A	BT	22 a	5	99
IRAT177	Normal	29 a	3	17
CNA-IRAT12A	BT	15 b	3	100

^a Mean percentages of 2 replications of 600 anthers each. Means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level. ^b Mean percentages of 3 observations of 100 pollen grains each. ^c Mean percentages of 3 bagged panicles.

This decrease in anther culturability of lines bearing the male sterile cytoplasm is the reverse of reports of

anther culturability in wheat and tobacco. □

Hybrid sterility in interracial and interspecific rice crosses

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Hybrid sterility in early generations of interracial and interspecific rice crosses is due to genic and cryptic structural hybridity. We examined the F₁s from eight japonica/indica, six japonica/japonica-indica, and two interspecific crosses during Jun-Sep 1988.

Spikelet sterility at harvest was 37.5-91.6%. Grain fertility was 8.4-62.5% (see table). Grain fertility of the

parents was 85.9-95.5%. In crosses involving the same parent as male or female, grain fertility differed greatly because of gene interaction.

Derivatives of japonica/indica crosses crossed with japonicas behaved like indicas and did not improve grain fertility, except in Nakate Shinsenbon/Ponni (fertility = 62.5%).

Hybrid sterility in the F₁ makes it difficult to generate large numbers of F₂ plants with desirable characters. Anther culture of F₁ hybrids to capture difficult-to-recover plant characters and to gain quick homozygosity is being attempted using F₁ stubbles of these interracial and interspecific crosses. □

Fertility in the F₁ of interracial, interspecific rice crosses. Coimbatore, Tamil Nadu, India, 1988.

Cross	F ₁ grain fertility (%)
<i>Japonica/indica</i>	
Norin 8/TKM6-35 kr.	42.1
Norin 8/IR50	21.0
Zuhio/ASD16	8.4
Zuhio/CO 37	11.1
Zuhio/IR50	12.1
Oozora/CO 37	47.6
Oozora/IR50	11.3
Nakate Shinsenbon/IR50	26.2
<i>Japonica/japonica-indica</i>	
Norin 6/Ponni	10.7
Norin 6/Ponni dwarf	14.8
Norin 8/White Ponni	39.8
Norin 8/Ponni dwarf	13.4
Oozora/Ponni	19.1
Nakate Shinsenbo/Ponni	62.5
<i>Interspecific</i>	
<i>O. sativa f. spontanea</i> /ADT 37	11.7
<i>O. sativa f. spontanea</i> /Ponni dwarf	14.1

Using metroglyph analysis to study variability in early generations of rainfed lowland rice

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We studied the morphological variations in 12 F₂ families obtained from 9 parents under semidry conditions in 1988. Panicle length, tillers per plant, plant height, and single plant yield were recorded from 50 single plants per family selected for extreme differences (see table).

Variability in the F₂ populations was expressed in metroglyph analysis using score indices. A scatter diagram was

plotted using plant height as the ordinate and single plant yield as the abscissa. Variation in other characters was represented by range and direction (see figure).

Index values for the range of variability were partitioned into four groups using class intervals. The range of variation was wider in Norungan/IR50 (index value 15) and IR29/IR50 (index value 13).